

The theory and practice of computational errors

This talk offers a taxonomy of computing errors based on the level of control we have over the computing method. Error control can be achieved by theoretical, mathematical means but also by practical engineering means. It is far from clear that theoretical error control is epistemically superior to its pragmatic cousin. To underline this point several successful and widely employed computing methods where only pragmatic error control is achieved are examined

Abstract:

All computing methods produce errors. But not all errors are treated the same way. Some numerical errors for example can be easily accounted for by relying on mathematically established error bounds. Such error bounds often state a trade-off between accuracy and computational feasibility. The longer you let the method run or the more processing power you invest the better your result will be. This is mathematically guaranteed. In many cases such straightforward results cannot be established because one is unable to calculate the difference between the true result and the numerical result. For example, where exact solutions to differential equations are unknown, this so-called forward error cannot be computed.

A work-around is perturbing the original problem into something that would have been exactly solved by the numerical method. Instead of the difference between the true result and the numerical result this yields the so-called backward error, a perturbation of the original problem. It can then be decided if this perturbation is acceptable or if the numerical method has to be adapted. The epistemic relevance of the backward error concept has been pointed out repeatedly by Fillion (Fillion, N. (2011), Fillion, N., Corless, R.M. (2021)).

Even this basic distinction between forward and backward error induces an epistemic hierarchy. Prima facie we should prefer methods where forward error can be calculated and of course we should prefer methods which produce less error.

In distinction from Fillion and Bangu's explanation (Fillion, N., & Bangu, S. (2015)) I propose to view epistemic hierarchies to arise specifically from the loss of error control over the computational method. Forward or backward numerical errors in some of the most widely used computing methods (Monte Carlo, artificial neural nets) are completely uncontrolled, we don't have mathematically established error bounds on them.

This leads to the following puzzling observation: If numerical errors are uncontrolled for, why are these methods used so widely? What is their epistemic gain?

To dissolve this puzzle I define error control as a broader notion than e.g. numerical stability, modelling requirements or outright numerical error. It can incorporate knowledge gained from deploying the method but also tacit engineering and design knowledge. I argue that we can gain error control by applying a method instead of theorizing about it. This claim I will illustrate with several examples ranging from computer simulations to ML methods. The epistemic hierarchy is then induced by the amount of error control we can achieve. Theoretical shortcomings can be ameliorated by practice and vice versa.

Fillion, N. (2011). "Backward Error Analysis as a Model of Computation for Numerical Methods"
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Fillion, N., Corless, R.M. (2021) Concepts of Solution and the Finite Element Method: a Philosophical
Take on Variational Crimes. *Philos. Technol.* 34, 129–148 . <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00371-w>

Fillion, N., & Bangu, S. (2015). Numerical Methods, Complexity, and Epistemic Hierarchies. *Philosophy
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